

Sweetgrass Cultural Protocol

Advice for Good Relations with a Culturally Significant Relative

Acknowledgements

The Sweetgrass Cultural Protocol was created to help start a new practice of protecting Indigenous knowledge, Indigenous cultural and intellectual property, Indigenous data and Indigenous expertise shared within research projects. The protocol makes clear some of the obligations and responsibilities that Acadia National Park has to support the Wabanaki Sweetgrass Gatherers, the sweetgrass itself and for all the non-human relatives that live in and depend upon the saltmarsh as culturally and environmentally significant places. The Protocol sets out guidance and directions for current and future research on these traditional Wabanaki Homelands. The themes in this Protocol were identified by the Wabanaki Sweetgrass Gatherers. It reflects over four years of conversations identifying concerns and developing strategies that properly acknowledge, attribute and recognize the authority of generational care and knowledge around sweetgrass. This Protocol has an accompanying film featuring the ideas and thoughts of the Wabanaki Sweetgrass Gatherers on similar themes.

This protocol was developed by Jane Anderson with the Wabanaki Sweetgrass Gatherers: Molly Neptune Parker, Geo Neptune, Gal Frey, Gabe Frey, Suzanne Greenlaw, Rhonda London, Rocky Bear, John Neptune, Gabe Paul, Nicole Paul, Sarah Sockbeson, Pat Alamenas, Jennifer Neptune, Carol Dana, Kim Bryant, Natalie Lolar, Kyle Lolar, Tania Morey and Paula Thorne.

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Ancestral Homelands

I really feel that sense of going home when I go there, and I've felt like that since I was a kid.

- Geo Neptune (Passamaquoddy)

The Passamaquoddy Tribes at Motahkomikuk (Indian Township) and at Sipayik, the Penobscot Nation, Mi'kmaq Nation and the Houlton Band of Maliseet Indians are collectively known as the Wabanaki Nations. The Wabanaki Nations have lived for thousands of years in the lands and waters now called Maine. Despite colonization and attempted genocide—including the forced removal of children—the Wabanaki Nations have endured as sovereign and self-determining peoples, with distinct and diverse languages, cultures, governments, and economic structures.

Wabanaki Peoples are active stewards of these lands and waters and have extensive knowledge and expertise in caring for and sustaining the environment for all human and other than human lives. These are Ancestral Homelands which have been cared for, cultivated and tended to by Wabanaki Peoples for generations.

National Parks and Indigenous Peoples

It's stolen land, and getting reconnected to it is like...You see how the grass responds, it's revitalizing it.

- Gabe Frey (Passamaquoddy)

All America's National Parks are on traditional Indigenous lands. While they comprise only a fraction of the land that was stolen from Indigenous Peoples, they are significant in the larger story of Indigenous dispossession.¹ Every National Park has a human history and is a cultural landscape actively created through long-term Indigenous stewardship and relations.

Acadia National Park was created in 1916. This designation radically changed Wabanaki access to these lands. For example, it meant that seasonal camps for hunting, fishing and gathering were prohibited. Access to saltmarshes and sweetgrass became more difficult across the state and it remains a significant challenge to Wabanaki Peoples today. Passed by Congress, the 1916 National Park Service Organic Act enshrined a logic of conservation and preservation (non-impairment) and brought uniformity to the administration of the Parks system. Neither 'conservation' or 'non-impairment' were defined in the Act. These logics of conservation and preservation have been harmful to Indigenous Peoples and created a perception of Indigenous absence. This is in contrast to the reality of ongoing Indigenous stewardship practices that this project, and others currently underway, center.

Acadia National Park is leading the way in creating new initiatives that recognize these legacies of exclusion. Acadia National Park is actively working with the Wabanaki Nations to establish new and meaningful relationships that support and enable the reconnection of these lands with Wabanaki Peoples.

[1] David Treuer (2021), "Return the National Parks to the Tribes" The Atlantic May Issue.

Sweetgrass

It is not just some plant or some grass. It is a relative. It has a purpose in our culture.

- Nicole Paul (Passamaquoddy)

wəli-mskihkəwal - Penobscot-Abenaki (the good grass)

welimahaskil - Passamaquoddy-Maliseet

suwitokolasol - Passamaquoddy-Maliseet

weljemajgewe'l - Mi'kmaq

Sweetgrass (the good grass) is a perennial grass that grows in saltwater marshes along the coast of what is currently called Maine and New Brunswick. It is a culturally significant species. For Wabanaki Peoples sweetgrass is a relative and its strength and vitality has been integral to Wabanaki culture for generations. Sweetgrass is used in a variety of ways including for basketry and ceremony.

Sweetgrass gathering is a unique cultural practice that has been developed and refined over thousands of years. Care and love for the grass by the gatherers, and by the grass for the gatherers, makes a reciprocal relationship of giving and caring. For gatherers the health of sweetgrass is a priority. Gathering is a careful and culturally connected practice. Sweetgrass gathering is taught over time from Ancestors to Elders to Children who then teach the next generations.

Background to the Project

The energy that you harvest sweetgrass with, is in the sweetgrass itself... harvesting or picking sweetgrass is an act of love.
- Suzanne Greenlaw (Maliseet)

In 2016 Acadia National Park and a collective of Wabanaki Sweetgrass Gatherers initiated a project to assess the environmental impact of traditional harvesting practices on sweetgrass in a designated marsh in the National Park. The project was led by Suzanne Greenlaw (Maliseet), University of Maine and Michelle Baumflek, US Forest Service with Rebecca Cole-Will, Acadia Cultural Resources Specialist. It conclusively demonstrated that the traditional and contemporary Wabanaki cultural practices of harvesting supported the health of the sweetgrass and of surrounding species. The project demonstrated that sweetgrass responds positively to being harvested and actively requires harvesting and care to better thrive.

Cultural Protocol

The land wants us back.
- Donald Soctomah (Passamaquoddy)

Cultural protocols reflect Indigenous cultural values and create the basis for Indigenous re-worlding. Protocols center Indigenous sovereign interests to support the formation of different equitable relationships. They provide guidance and advice for decision-making, governance and appropriate research.

In contexts of research and the sharing, usage and storage of Indigenous knowledge, data and cultural practices, cultural protocols outline expectations around Indigenous rights in cultural knowledge and resource use and help build better and more respectful relationships with Indigenous peoples.

This Protocol is not legally binding. It reflects the broader concerns of the collective of Wabanaki Sweetgrass Gatherers. As sovereign entities, Tribal Nations enter into individual government to government agreements with the

National Park Service and the Department of Interior. Government to government agreements will be necessary in particular areas for safeguarding sweetgrass in Acadia National Park, especially in the context of permits and future co-management activities. This Protocol conveys advice and guidance to support those agreements as appropriate. It does not replace this direct sovereign agreement making process.

The Role, Significance and Value of Indigenous Knowledge

They proved what we said all along. We make it healthier and better. It is a reciprocal relationship. The grass needs us as much as we need the grass. We value each other.
- Jenn Neptune (Penobscot)

Indigenous knowledge, or Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK) are terms that can be used interchangeably. It is a dynamic way of knowing involving generations of knowledge in one location, generally passed down through oral tradition. TEK is very context-specific; information is not disseminated across a whole species range. While Indigenous Peoples manage areas collectively, and work as a whole, there is a vast range of variation of knowledge and variation of practice. This kind of variation can be a challenge within Western Science contexts. Often statistical analysis does not corroborate easily with TEK in part because of the variation.

Indigenous Cultural and Intellectual Property

Indigenous Cultural and Intellectual Property (ICIP) generally refers to moral and legal rights and interests that Indigenous Peoples assert in order to protect Indigenous Peoples' knowledge, data and cultural practices from misuse. Misuse means when knowledge, data and cultural practices are used in ways that were not intended and are disrespectful. Misuse includes, but is not limited to: derogatory treatment, including the use of Indigenous Peoples' knowledge, data and cultural practices in a way that undermines the originally intended meaning; appropriation, involves the use of Indigenous Peoples' knowledge, data and cultural practices for purposes that are unintended by the original creator/s and can cause cultural, emotional, and psychological harm to Indigenous Peoples; and misattribution, including not properly acknowledging, naming or recognizing knowledge holders and where information has come from, including missing or incorrect attribution and association of Indigenous Peoples.

The Wabanaki Sweetgrass Gatherers assert the perpetual right to be recognized, acknowledged, named, and associated with this project, the project results, the project data and all products connected to this project.

There can also be friction between Western Science and TEK in the words that are used. Trying to remain abstract, disconnected and removed in an attempt to appear neutral and objective, Western Science can be cold and prescriptive. TEK reflects a different way of connection and value systems. Indigenous cosmology, relationships and inherent contextual knowledge are included as key elements. For example, in a simple harvest or gathering lesson, there are ethics, morals, biology, species diversity and harvesting impacts that are included. In Western Science, it's more segregated. The researcher may not be there year after year or season after season and so can miss important localized changes. The researcher might also only focus on one species not others around it, nor the health of the soil or the water also affecting the life of the species. Harvesters return year after year, often to the same place. They see the impact of their activity and adjust so it's sustainable.²

In December 2022, the White House Council on Environmental Quality (CEQ) and the White House Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP) jointly released new guidance including an implementation memorandum for federal agencies focusing on recognizing and including Indigenous Ecological Knowledge in federal research, policy and decision making.³ This guidance formalizes the inclusion of Indigenous knowledge as providing important information for research and decision-making. It asks that Indigenous knowledge is properly credited and acknowledged.

[2] Adapted from Suzanne Greenlaw interview in WildSeeds.

[3] <https://www.whitehouse.gov/ceq/news-updates/2022/12/01/white-house-releases-first-of-a-kind-indigenous-knowledge-guidance-for-federal-agencies/>

Education

On June 15, 2001, the Maine State Legislature enacted a landmark law, now known as the Wabanaki Studies Law, which requires schools to teach Maine K–12 students about Wabanaki territories, economic systems, cultural systems, governments, and political systems, as well as the Wabanaki Nation’s relationships with local, state, national, and international governments. The Wabanaki Studies Law, now codified at 20-A M.R.S. § 4706(2), is critical to overcoming stereotypes and ignorance about Indigenous peoples, which are harmful to Wabanaki students and non-Native students alike.

This law was created to address the lack of education about Wabanaki Nations in schools, in the first instance. Misunderstanding and lack of education also exist in other contexts across the State. This project provides an important opportunity to initiate education programs focused on:

- The value and significance of Traditional Ecological Knowledge as/in science;
- Sweetgrass as a culturally significant species,
- Wabanaki plant and animal relationships of care and;
- Unique Wabanaki environmental stewardship.

For the development of future relationships and to advance the federal guidance on TEK , there is a significant need for education and training in two key areas.

- 1. Acadia National Park staff.** Staff need specific education and training around Wabanaki histories, cultural practices and environmental stewardship.
- 2. Visitors to the National Park.** Many visitors travel from other states and around the world to visit Acadia. There is a clear opportunity to increase education, awareness and understanding about Wabanaki rights and interests in keeping with the Wabanaki Studies Law.

Educational Opportunities for Acadia National Park Service Staff

The Wabanaki Nations have different relationships to the National Park and are not ‘visitors’. Special care and awareness by National Park Service staff is required to understand the Park as Wabanaki Homelands and the special relationships that Wabanaki Peoples retain to these lands and waters. Specialized cultural awareness training should be developed and delivered to all Acadia Park Service staff. This training should be provided to all new incoming staff and there should be continued learning opportunities. This training should have specific modules that address areas including but not limited to: sweetgrass gathering methodologies and practices; archaeology and Wabanaki history; Indigenous cultural and intellectual property; Indigenous worldviews and care of species.⁴

This Protocol recommends the development of Park specific education and training to better support Wabanaki stewardship of culturally specific species. This education and training will also be critical for future co-management relationships to develop. There is a responsibility that Acadia National Park has to educate staff internally whilst simultaneously building new educational opportunities for its non-Native visitors.

[4] In 2023, the National Park Foundation began offering training on tribal consultation.

Visitors to National Park

For Wabanaki Sweetgrass Gatherers to feel safe and respected as they regain cultural rights to gather and maintain cultural practices, visitors to Acadia must also be provided with information about these changing relationships in the Park. This awareness building could happen through four different kinds of information dissemination activities.

1. A Sweetgrass Information Guide could be developed as a small informational pamphlet that could be provided to visitors that enter through regulated Park entry points and at the Visitor Center locations. The same information guide could be added to the Acadia NP website.
2. The Sweetgrass Protocol Film can be adapted and made available to NPS for viewing online and in Visitor Centers and for the Friends of Acadia National Park.
3. Scheduling more Wabanaki speakers and topics as part of the Schoodic Research Institute events.
4. Friends of Acadia National Park could also feature the Sweetgrass Protocol film and commit to a new initiative to incorporate more educational activities as part of its responsibilities.

Representation and Permission to Use Images

Over the course of this research, a variety of photographs of Wabanaki Sweetgrass Gatherers have been taken. Some of these have been used in reports with individual and group permission. The photographer does not exclusively have control over the use of these photographs.

The Wabanaki Sweetgrass Gatherers assert their rights to not have these photographs used in other contexts, or circulated without their consent. Individual permission must be obtained for future use. Any use of the photographs should ensure that individuals are properly named with their Tribal citizen affiliation/s and the name of the research project. The Wabanaki Sweetgrass Gatherers will collectively decide on the photographs that Acadia Park Service can share, with proper attribution, for use in other

contexts where this research project is featured and celebrated.

Film Footage

Andreas Burgess was commissioned to make the Sweetgrass Protocol Film that reflects Wabanaki Sweetgrass Gatherer's voices and unique expectations – from caring for sites to privacy when gathering and use of sweetgrass as cultural practice. The film footage remains the property of the Wabanaki Sweetgrass Gatherers and hard drives of the footage will be provided to each THPO for safe-keeping and future use. Footage can be used by Gatherers for other purposes as needed with acknowledgement of Andreas Burgess as the original film-maker.

Ownership of Research Data

Indigenous Peoples' Data means information and knowledges recorded on any medium and in any format that comprise information, specimens, and knowledges about non-humans with which Indigenous Peoples have relations; information about Indigenous individuals; and, information and knowledges about Indigenous Peoples as collectives. Indigenous Peoples' Data ranges from traditional and contemporary writings and performances to languages, oral traditions, and ceremonies, living and nonliving specimens and environmental data.

Indigenous Peoples' Data collected in this project and in the future, will be

held by each Tribal Nation. Use will be determined through Tribal decision-making processes. Tribal Nations will retain full control, governance and decision-making capacity over this data. Agreements around future use of data will be negotiated through General Agreements and other mechanisms that are determined through community-driven processes. Tribal ownership of research data will be incorporated into future research permits for any projects conducted in Acadia National Park.

Permit System

The National Park Service requires that there is a permit system in place to gather sweetgrass. The exact details of the permit system will be specific to each Tribal Nation and will require an independent government to government agreement.

The following recommendations are made for the development of any permit system:

1. The Permit system should be co-developed with Gatherers;
2. The Permit system should not overburden the Tribal Nation or the THPO;
3. The Permit system should be straightforward and easy for a Gatherer to use;
4. The Permit system should factor in limited access to computers and printers to print off permits.

Privacy

Question: How would you want law enforcement to engage with you when you are out here [in the marsh]?

- Suzanne Greenlaw (Maliseet)

Answer: I wouldn't.

- Gabe Frey (Passamaquoddy)

Gathering is a cultural and spiritual practice that needs to be respected and requires privacy. All Acadia National Park Service Law Enforcement Rangers should be educated about sweetgrass gathering and specific notifications should be made when the season for gathering has started. National Park Service Law Enforcement Rangers should be made aware of sweetgrass gathering locations to support informed patrolling. Only when absolutely necessary should Law Enforcement Rangers approach gatherers in a salt-marsh.

This Protocol recommends the co-development of a specific training module for Acadia National Park Service Law Enforcement Rangers to support Rangers in recognizing and respecting privacy around sweetgrass harvesting. This includes creating new internal indicators that harvesting is underway and an educational strategy for protecting gatherers privacy when in the saltmarsh.

Monitoring

*The grass remembers you.
- Jenn Neptune (Penobscot)*

The National Park Service requires yearly monitoring of sweetgrass to help ensure the ongoing health of the species. Monitoring strategies should be co-developed with Gatherers to limit the potential of monitoring to feel like it is surveillance of the Gatherers. The Park staff and the Gatherers are all aligned in supporting the health and future of the grass and to safeguard against over-picking. Monitoring could include annual tribal Nation reporting of sweetgrass harvesting amounts to the Park Service and identification about changes in the marsh, including changes in water levels and the health and population of other species.

As sweetgrass saltmarshes are homes for many other species – jointly conceived monitoring processes would include more holistic accounts of changing conditions in the marsh. Monitoring could be another opportunity to value, support and recognize the importance of Indigenous knowledge.

Harvesting in a Good Way

*You never over-pick or over-harvest...just take a little bit for the season.
- Gabe Paul (Penobscot)*

Harvesting in a good way means being careful and sustainable, leaving the sweetgrass root systems to re-generate and re-grow. Not everyone has been taught how to harvest in a way that supports the health of sweetgrass. For some people, the teachings from Elders skipped a generation. The collective of Wabanaki Sweetgrass Gatherers will provide any guidance and support to other tribal citizens that is needed.

Towards Co-Stewardship

*This is our heaven.
- Tania Morey (Tobique First Nation- Neqotkuk)*

On November 15, 2021, Secretary Haaland and Secretary of Agriculture Vilsack issued Secretary's Order 3403. ⁵ The Secretary's Order directs agencies to increase opportunities for Tribes to participate in traditional stewardship of present-day federal lands and waters. This includes the integration of thousands of years of Indigenous knowledge and sustainability practices into federal management and operations, subject to the interest of each Tribal Nation.

Sweetgrass gathering is only one of many traditional cultural practices that can be reactivated on these Wabanaki Homelands. Jointly conceiving new National Park practices around land stewardship actively brings Indigenous knowledge, voice and expertise into Acadia National Park in deliberate ways that recognize Indigenous worldviews and relationships. First steps towards meaningful engagement and partnership will lead to the development of long-term co-stewardship models that recognize, value and protect Indigenous knowledge and living cultural practices. Formal co-management initiatives will need government to government agreements to be in place.

[5] Joint Secretarial Order on Fulfilling the Trust Responsibility to Indian Tribes in the Stewardship of Federal Lands and Waters (2021)

The National Park Service must actively center Wabanaki rights and interests in future planning, education and policy-making activities. Addressing the history of land dispossession in Maine requires building a pathway towards shared decision-making and authority with Tribal Nations.

Credits

Sweetgrass Gatherers

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Tribal and Historic Preservation Officers

Donald Soctomah – Passamaquoddy
Chris Sockalexix – Penobscot
Isaac St John – Maliseet
Jennifer Gaenzle - Mi'kmaq

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